

Table 1. Optimized distances (mm) between elements in a straight-line structure

d1	d2	d3	d4	d5	d6	d7	d8	d9
30.5	26.05	28.12	29.2	31.27	31.35	34.42	36.48	30.79

Table 2. Optimized distances (mm) between elements in a U-shaped structure

d1	d2	d3	d4	d5	d6	d7	d8	d9	d10	d11
35.5	30.56	31.27	32.8	21.29	50	21.59	37.57	34.27	30.86	27.9

Table 3. Optimized distances (mm) between elements in a one-sided V-shaped structure

d1	d2	d3	d4	d5	d6	d7	d8	d9	d10
25.5	36.05	37.12	41.2	50.12	28.62	40.14	42.8	44.58	16.3

Table 4. Optimized distances (mm) between elements in a one-sided V-shaped structure

d1	d2	d3	d4	d5	d6	d7	d8	d9	d10
30.5	21.05	36.2	41.2	51.12	20.5	48.9	18.3	37.58	2.5

Table 5. Comparison between the proposed structures in this paper

Structure	No. of elements	Element shape	Dimension in λ^2	Frequency range (GHz)	Band width	Maximum gain (dBi)	Maximum directivity (dBi)	Scale factor
Single element	1	Vivaldi	0.85×0.63	6.4 - 8.2	%27	4	4.7	-
Straight-line	8	Vivaldi	2.87×0.48	3 - 18	%142	6.26	7.7	1.05
U-shaped	8	Vivaldi	1.58×1.38	2.6 - 18	%149	8.3	12.5	1.05
One-sided V-shaped	8	Vivaldi	1.6×1.56	2.4 - 18	%152	7.61	11.8	1.05

Table 6. Comparison of the proposed U-shaped antenna with other log-periodic antennas

Ref.	No. of elements	Element shape	Dimension in λ^2	Frequency range (GHz)	Bandwidth	Maximum gain(dBi)	Maximum directivity (dBi)	Scale factor
Dadel, Srivastava, Tiwary (2011)	5	Square	1.06×0.56	2 - 2.5	%22	-	-	1.05
Dadel, Srivastava, Tiwary (2011)	7	Square	1.5×0.6	2 -2.8	%33	-	-	1.05
Dadel, Srivastava, Tiwary (2011)	9	Square	1.9×0.65	2 - 3.15	%44	-	-	1.05
Dadel, Srivastava (2011)	3	Rectangle	0.8×0.65	3.1- 7	%77	5.87	-	0.9
Dadel, Srivastava (2011)	5	Rectangle	0.9×0.85	3.1 - 5.7	%59	6.98	-	0.9
Ghanbari et al. (2013)	4	Square	0.96×0.64	2.4- 2.5	7.47%	2.75	7.05	1.03
Rahim et al. (2007)	3	Triangle	2.1×1.7	8.2- 11.2	%30	4.8	-	0.7- 0.98
Rahim et al. (2007)	5	Triangle	2.4×2.2	7.8- 11	%34	7.7	-	0.7- 0.98
Wang et al. (2008)	17	Square (straight-line)	2.85×0.95	3-8.5	%95	-	-	1.05
Wang et al. (2008)	17	Square (U-shaped)	1.85×1.4	3.5- 10	%96	-	-	1.05
Anuar et al. (2012)	11	Rectangle	2.25×0.9	3.2 - 5.8	%57	-	-	1.1
Anuar et al. (2012)	11	Ellipse	2.25×0.9	2.8- 5.2	%60	-	-	1.1
This work	8	Vivaldi	1.58×1.38	2.6 - 18	%149	8.3	12.5	1.05